

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Table of contents.....	3
2	Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	4
	Executive summary.....	5
3	Introduction: WP6.....	6
3.1	Objectives of WP6.....	6
3.2	WP6 activity.....	6
3.2.1	Deliverables and Milestones.....	7
4	Task 6.3: Training activities.....	9
4.1	Approach.....	9
4.2	Strategic Training Guidelines	9
4.3	Activities	10
4.3.1	EPMA Summer Schools.....	10
4.3.2	ASGMI events	16
4.3.3	Other training opportunities	19
4.3.3.1	Portuguese Society of Materials (SPM)	19
4.3.3.2	Training in synergy with clustered projects and initiatives	19
4.3.3.3	The START webinars.....	20
4.3.4	Final Workshop	20

2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of Task 6.3 “Training activities” in the period 1st May 2023 – 31st May 2023¹ (M12 of the START project).

During the period reported, that is only one month of activity, the kick-off of the training workflow happened. A document that is labelled “Strategic Training Guidelines” is being drafted and will be completed and approved in the next weeks. It outlines the protocol for the development of the training plan within the START project, with a dual objective: to ensure maximum visibility of the START project and the work that is being carried out, and to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge present within partners and generated by the project and to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists. The guidelines will ensure the highest quality of the training (and mentoring) actions so that the attendees and the project can benefit optimally.

On the practical side, some training events have already been outlined, with different levels of completion:

- A 30' START lecture during the EPMA 2023 Powder Metallurgy Summer School (Dresden, 17-21 July 2023) with an audience of 60 students.
- a presentation of the START project on 6th-8th September 2023 during the 2nd edition of the summer school “Materials for Energy Transition”, organised by the technical division “Materials for Energy” of the Portuguese Society of Materials in Porto, Portugal.

More training events are being imagined, especially:

- In the framework of the already existing experience of ASGMI in organizing workshops on Mining Environmental Liabilities, both in person and online (this may be organised in 2024 if not in 2025)
- In the framework of the clustering activities (Task 6.4) START will see if joint training activities can be organised together with other projects or initiatives that share some of the main interests of the project, like mine waste exploitation, raw materials issues, energy harvesting, green energy, etc.
- Other events not purely imagined as trainings (like the START webinars) will help educating on the topics of the project.
- The Final Training Workshop, focused on sustainability, close to the end of the project, whose organisation will not start before 2025.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to the last 2 weeks of May could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.8 (M24).

3 INTRODUCTION: WP6

3.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives of this work package are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

EPMA, leading the WP, ensures a broad dissemination of the project progress and outcomes in Europe through its well-established network and website and its annual events and frequent Sectoral and Working Group meetings, even after the completion of the project. Nevertheless, all partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

3.2 WP6 ACTIVITY

The activity of WP6 is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT of shows the start and end of each task. As can be seen, Tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.4 have already begun in the first months of the project, whereas Task 6.3 started just at M12 (and Task 6.5 only in Year 4, rather close to the end of the project).

3.2.1 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP contains a large number of deliverables, 15 out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but on the other hand only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022).

The deliverables, also visible in Figure 2 can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.4 is being presented at the end of M12, D6.6 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 is the present report, D6.8 upcoming in 12 months)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 08:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. This milestone has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1 submitted earlier and already accepted).

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026.

WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's we	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strat	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending

[Blue bar]	To be completed on the current year
[Yellow bar]	Deadline approaching
[Green bar]	Submitted
[Light Green bar]	Approved

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

4 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

4.1 APPROACH

This task aims to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge present within partners and generated by the project to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists. We will make use of established and new training activities, to funnel knowledge to students, young engineers, and experts:

- A strategic document on how to present, promote, call, recruit and orient and mentor young students and researchers into the project
- Project lectures during the EPMA PM Summer School². During the 4 years of the project, we plan to reach at least 200 students by this activity (normally 50-60 participants in each edition). This includes the preparation of a lecture, updated every year, about START activities.
- ASGMI has significant experience working with Mining Environmental Liabilities. In the past, several workshops and events have been organized on this topic³. ASGMI will develop learning material based on the already existing products & experience and will add new information and results from START (mainly from WP 2). The objective is to hold a free online seminar open to bachelor and master's degree young students where they can interact with the researchers, ask questions and learn details of the project.
- During a final Training Workshop for scientists and industry members, focused on sustainability of the developed know-how. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants.

Important: this task started in M12, and this deliverable is related just to the activity in this month, and some exceptional and very limited work carried out before the formal start of the task. Clearly, as the drafting and reviewing of the report by the consortium takes time, the content cannot include all that happened until the end of the month, but rather the activity in the first weeks. Any further detail will be reported in D6.8 due at M24.

4.2 STRATEGIC TRAINING GUIDELINES

A document named "Strategic Training Guidelines" is being drafted collaboratively using the START project SharePoint. This is an important first step in order to take a uniform approach to the topic, avoid errors and maximise the impact of the training activities.

The document contains at the moment the following chapters:

- Plan for training within START. Main training events and tools, expected participation and targets, scope of the trainings, evaluation of training, reporting of training.
- Guidelines for training: how to present, promote.

² <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

³ <https://asgmi.org/grupo-de-expertos-en-pasivosambientales-mineros-2/>

- Guidelines for mentoring: how to call, recruit and mentor.

The document will be completed and approved in the following weeks.

4.3 ACTIVITIES

The activity in training run along a few different lines, relying on the expertise of some key training partners, with experience in organising training events, for students of different levels and for experienced and educated trainees.

4.3.1 EPMA Summer Schools

The EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School⁴ is organised by the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA) with support from its members. In fact, founded in 1989, EPMA is the leading powder metallurgy (PM) trade association representing the interests of the entire European PM community, and promoting PM technology throughout the world.

The EPMA PM Summer Schools have been designed to offer participants from all parts of Europe an advanced teaching of PM's advantages and limitations by some of the leading academic and industrial personnel in Europe. They also are a rare opportunity to stimulate direct technical discussions by young scientists and engineers who are interested in broadening their knowledge through interaction with senior figures in the PM industry.

Since 1998, about 1000 young graduates from both industry and academia from all over Europe have attended these summer schools and had the opportunity to meet and learn from some of PM's leading experts.

The first editions were actually supported by EU programmes like the Marie Curie. After some successful EU-funded editions, EPMA started organizing the school without other funding than student fees and some small sponsoring to cover expenses for some material distributed to them.

After a two-years stop in 2020 and 2021 due to Covid (it was decided that the school could not be run virtually because it would have been totally different and much less effective both for the learning and for the networking aspects), the school successfully restarted in 2022. The 2023 edition, that will be held in Dresden, is the 21st in the series. Each year the school is organised in a different location, chosen among the most relevant academic and industrial reference centres for PM (Figure 3).

The school is held normally in June or July, lasting one week (arrival on Sunday, departure Friday afternoon), and presents an in depth overview of PM by encompassing lectures (more than 25, each given by outstanding speakers both from academy and industry), lab experiences (2 afternoons, organised in the premises of the hosting entity), a students' posters area to exchange info about participants' current activities, and lab or factory visits to nearby PM-relevant institutes or companies. The whole course is conducted so that maximum interaction amongst trainers and trainees, and among trainees, can happen, in a not-too-formal environment.

⁴ <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

The students in the school are supposed to have the main knowledge of physics, engineering and chemistry of materials (structure of metals and their physical and mechanical properties, basic inorganic chemistry, phase diagrams, etc.).

For many Summer School alumni, the experience at the School proved to be an important step of their career, allowing them to get in touch with peers, learn about powder metallurgy processes that they normally do not experience directly in their career, establish long-term collaborations, and profit of direct exchanges with experienced professionals. Many of them took part again later, becoming a lecturer.

For practical reasons, normally driven by the organisation of the experiences in the lab, the participation is usually limited to 60 trainees.

Edition	Year	City	Country
1	1998	Meissen	Germany
2	1999	Gothenburg	Sweden
	2000	-	
3	2001	San Sebastián	Spain
4	2002	Vienna	Austria
	2003	-	
	2004	-	
5	2005	Aachen	Germany
6	2006	Grenoble	France
7	2007	Košice	Slovakia
8	2008	Acqui Terme	Italy
9	2009	Košice	Slovakia
10	2010	Madrid	Spain
11	2011	Dresden	Germany
12	2012	San Sebastián	Spain
13	2013	Trento	Italy
14	2014	Krakow	Poland
15	2015	Sheffield	UK
16	2016	Valencia	Spain
17	2017	Grenoble	France
18	2018	Vienna	Austria
19	2019	Trento	Italy
	2020	- Covid -	
	2021	- Covid -	
20	2022	Ciudad Real	Spain
21	2023	Dresden	Germany

Figure 3: Left: list of all Summer Schools organised by EPMA. Right: brochure of the first edition 1998, in Meissen (Dresden, Germany).

The course fee, that is depending on the category the participant fits in (Academics & Research Centres, entities or individuals that are EPMA Members, entities or individuals that are Non-Members, PM End Users) includes all relevant course documents, five nights hotel accommodation (single occupancy), refreshments, a Welcome Reception on Monday and the Summer School networking dinner on Thursday evening. A certificate is issued to each trainee at the end, stating that the participant has successfully taken part in the course (no evaluation is carried out). In addition to that, the fee also includes 18 months' Student Membership of the EPMA, which enables members to obtain discounted rates at the Euro PM Congress & Exhibition and all EPMA events, amongst other benefits. Applicants have to fill a form in the EPMA Summer School website, generally between January and May of the year in which they intend to take part; as the applications

normally outnumber the available places, a selection is made after the deadline and successful applications are notified, whilst the remaining are entitled to priority for next editions.

During the START project, EPMA has planned of hosting information about the project and its connected topics (thermoelectrics in particular) in the technical programme.

In 2022 the school was due just after the beginning of the activities, and it had already been organised. So, only a quick information about START – one slide with the general features of the project, its approach, expected results and impact, its relevance for the Green Deal - was given by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his initial address to the attendees (60 plus the speakers and the local organizers) in the 2022 edition of the Summer School, that was held from 20th to 24th June in Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in Ciudad Real (Spain) (Figure 4, Figure 5).

Figure 4: Attendees and speakers at the EPMA Summer School 2022.

Figure 5: B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during the opening speech at the EPMA Summer School 2022, that included a slide on the project.

For the following editions, 2024, 2025, and beyond, the START content will be more significant. It is planned to have lectures, but also some practical experience could be organised in later editions.

In 2023 the EPMA Summer School will be held in Dresden (Germany), in the premises of the Fraunhofer institute IFAM (Institut für Angewandte Materialien, Institute for Applied Materials), on 17th-21st July. 102 potential trainees applied within the deadline of 3rd May 2023 to be selected among the 60 that will come to Dresden, so the school is largely overbooked, and all spots will be filled once again.

The programme has been arranged by EPMA, together with some academic EPMA members that take care of the technical content of the school, and is available in Figure 6.

START will be presented again by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his opening speech on Monday 17th July, as happened in 2022.

Among the several lectures there are topics that are relevant for START (“Powder Manufacturing and Characterization”, “Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering”), but on the project’s side on Friday 21st, 13:00 – 13:30, H. Yin (TEGnology) and A. Bianchin (MBN) will close the lectures by giving a presentation titled “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project”.

After the school, a feedback questionnaire is always circulated, where detailed evaluation of all lectures will be asked, under several aspects, so there will be feedback also on the START presentation. On the other hand, as no evaluation of students’ actual learning during the school is carried out, we will have no real feedback on that, nor on the impact of the learning. We might have a specific START feedback “offline” questionnaire with additional questions, but it will not be a real evaluation test as the school schedule does not allow to organise such an activity on site.

For 2024 and 2025 (and also for next years in case, although they will fall after the end of the project), as mentioned, the plan is to try including something about thermoelectric materials in the practical experiences (two afternoons in the programme are dedicated to lab experiences for the students, see the programme included for 2023). A provisional structure of that experience could include a few introductory words to explain what waste heat is, what are thermoelectric materials and how they can be produced (with a focus on PM routes, as this is the target of the school), and then a small demo experience with the use of a thermoelectric device on a heated surface (a furnace wall, an exhaust pipe, etc.) to show how electricity can be harvested using waste heat.

A detailed experience plan will be prepared later in the project collaborating with the companies that fabricate the TE devices and the PM-related partners.

Powder Metallurgy Summer School

17 July - 21 July 2023 - Dresden, Germany

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Programme

Please note this programme may be subject to change.

Monday 17 July

Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:00	Presentation of EPMA & IFAM	Dr Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA) & Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
09:00 - 10:00	Introduction to Materials Science	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
10:00 - 11:00	Introduction to PM	Prof Marco Actis Grande (Politecnico di Torino)
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee Break	
11:30 - 12:30	Powder Manufacturing and Characterization	Dr Dimitris Chasoglou (Hoganas AB)
12:30 - 13:30	Shaping Technologies	Dr Jose Manuel Sanchez Moreno (CEIT)
13:30 - 14:30	Lunch	
14:30 - 15:30	Fundamentals of Sintering	Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden; TU Dresden)
15:30 - 16:30	Liquid Phase Sintering	Dr Johannes Trapp (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
16:30 - 17:30	Coffee Break in Poster Area	
19:30 - 21:30	Welcome Reception	

Tuesday 18 July

Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Sintering Atmospheres	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
09:30 - 10:30	Post Sintering Treatments	Prof Monika Campos (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Properties of PM Parts	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
12:00 - 13:00	Furnace Technology	Mr Michael Kanaan (CREMER Thermoprozessanlagen)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Calphad Method in PM	Prof Raquel Oro de Calderon (TU Wien)
15:00 - 16:00	Modeling	Prof Dr Christoph Broeckmann (RWTH Aachen University)
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee Break	
16:30 - 17:30	Hot Isostatic Pressing	Mr Anders Magnusson (Quintus Technologies)
17:30 - 19:00	Lab Tour	
19:00 - 22:00	Social Evening	

Wednesday 19 July

Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Metal Injection Molding (I)	Prof Gemma Herranz (UCLM Spain)
09:30 - 10:30	Metal Injection Molding (II): Case studies, innovations and new frontiers	Prof Frank Petzoldt (Fraunhofer IFAM)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Additive Manufacturing (I) LPBF and SEBM	Mrs Marie Franke-Jürsch (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
12:00 - 13:00	Additive Manufacturing (II) Sinterbased AM Technologies	Dr Thomas Studnibz (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Sustainability in PM	Mr Babak Kianian (Hoganas AB)
15:00 - 16:30	Group A - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
15:00 - 16:30	Group B - Lab Work	
16:30 - 17:00	Coffee Break	
17:00 - 18:30	Group A - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
17:00 - 18:30	Group B - Lab Work	
19:00 - 22:00	Dinner	

Thursday 20 July

Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Low Alloy Steels	Prof Herbert Dänninger (TU Wien)
09:30 - 10:30	Special Steels	Dr Inigo Iturriza (CEIT)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Light Metals	Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden; TU Dresden)
12:00 - 13:00	High Temperature Materials	Prof José Manuel Torralba (IMDEA)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering	Prof Lars Nyborg (Chalmers)
15:00 - 16:30	Group B - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
15:00 - 16:30	Group A - Lab Work	
16:30 - 17:00	Coffee Break	
17:00 - 18:30	Group B - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
17:00 - 18:30	Group A - Lab Work	

Friday 21 July

Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	PM Materials for Hydrogen Production	Dr Christian Bernackner (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
09:30 - 10:30	PM Materials for Hydrogen Storage	Dr Felix Heubner (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Hard Materials	Dr Steven Moseley (Hill AG)
12:00 - 13:00	Soft Magnetic Materials	Dr Mark Dougan (AMES SA)
13:00 - 13:30	Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project	Mr Hao Yin (TEGnology) & Mr Avise Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia)
13:30 - 14:00	Certificates distribution	
14:00 - 15:00	Lunch	

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Figure 6: Programme of the EPMA Summer School 2023 in Dresden, Germany.

4.3.2 ASGMI events

ASGMI has extensive experience in organizing workshops, both virtual and face-to-face, on various topics related to mineral resources and mining environmental liabilities which are among the subject of work for the expert groups that are part of the Association.

Since 2006, ASGMI has held an average of two workshops per year, which were initially held in person. However, since 2020, due to the pandemic and the inability to travel, virtual workshops have been organized that are open to the entire scientific community and have had a significant impact on the Geological Surveys that are part of ASGMI, as well as the Association itself, due to their great acceptance with a registration volume of up to 600 people and more than 40% attendance throughout the event in most cases.

These virtual workshops were attended mainly by professionals belonging to Geological Surveys, professionals from private companies, and to a very large extent, students from the main universities of each country.

Some of the most relevant workshops for the project's topic include the workshop on "*The role of national geological services in relation to geological and mining resources, groundwater, and environmental quality*" held in Cartagena de Indias (Colombia) in October 2006, or the seminar on the "*Mission of geological services in the exploration of mineral deposits*" held in Lima (Peru) in May 2007.

Figure 7: Attendees of the workshop "*Mission of geological services in the exploration of mineral deposits*" held in Lima (Peru) in May 2007.

The workshops on "*Environmental evaluation and recovery of mining areas. Mining environmental liabilities*" held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra (Bolivia) in October 2008 (in its first edition) and a year

later the second edition, and in 2010 the third edition of the same workshop, are of special importance. As a result of these workshops, agreements were signed that led to the creation of the Expert Group on Environmental Liabilities of ASGMI with the purpose of developing methodological guidelines for the identification, characterization, and reuse of mining environmental liabilities.

In 2011 and 2013, the following workshops related to sustainability in mining were also held:

- *"Technical Conference on Geological Infrastructure, Mining, Environment and Sustainability"*, held in the context of the XVII Ordinary General Assembly of ASGMI (Mexico, April 2011)
- *"Geological Infrastructure, Mining and Environment: The role of National Geological Surveys in the face of mining conflicts"* (Argentina, October 2013)

In 2017, in collaboration with CIRDI (Canadian International Resources and Development Institute), the workshop *"The role of geological surveys in relation to artisanal and informal mining and mining conflicts"* was also held in person.

Starting in 2020, as mentioned earlier, successful virtual workshops open to the geoscientific community began to be held.

In September, the *"Virtual International Workshop on Mining Environmental Liabilities: Towards Sustainable Management. Global Vision in Ibero-America"* was of great relevance, as among the attendees were authorities from international organizations such as CEPAL. Following the workshop, a close [collaboration between CEPAL and ASGMI](#) was initiated within the MINSUS project for regional cooperation for the sustainable management of mining resources in Andean countries, carried out together with the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources - BGR.

Members of ASGMI's Expert Group on Mining Environmental Liabilities participated as speakers in the following events:

- Event: *"Pressures on biodiversity and ecosystems: towards proper sustainable management of MELs"* (March 2022)
- Regional Event *"Challenges for the sustainable management of mining environmental liabilities"*, from August 1st to 4th, 2022 in Lima (Peru).

On the other hand, ASGMI, through its Expert Group on Metallogeny and Mineral Resources - GEMET-, held in November 2021, the seminar *"Critical and Strategic Minerals in Ibero-America"* with the main objectives of understanding the state of knowledge about critical and strategic minerals and metals resources in Ibero-America and presenting case studies carried out by different Geological Surveys.

The Seminar aimed to be a space for dissemination of the type of information available in the Geological Surveys of Ibero-America and their degree of analysis and interpretation. The results of this event marked the starting point for the development of the map of critical minerals in Ibero-America and for the consolidation of the work towards a greater and better understanding of the potential of critical minerals in Latin America.

This meeting also had the external participation of the European Commission, the Association of Geological Surveys of Europe (EuroGeoSurveys), and the United States Geological Survey

(USGS), whose contribution and suggestions completed and reinforced the activities carried out by GEMET on this subject.

In addition, ASGMI participates in the EU-Latin America Partnership on Raw Materials project, within which high-level events have been organized in which ASGMI experts have participated as keynote speakers.

- EU-Latin America and the Caribbean Political Dialogue on the Identification of Strategic and Critical Raw Materials and the EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials (Chile, Nov 2022).
- 2nd EU-Latin America and the Caribbean Political Dialogue on the Identification of Strategic and Critical Raw Materials and the EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials (Argentina, May 2023).

Figure 8: 2nd EU-Latin America and the Caribbean Political Dialogue on the Identification of Strategic and Critical Raw Materials and the EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials (Argentina, May 2023).

Under this experience, virtual workshops within the framework of the START project, aimed at the academic community, specifically university or graduate students will be organized. The Expert Group on Mining Environmental Liabilities as well as the Mineral Resources Expert Group, which includes members from different countries in Latin America, Spain, and Portugal, can participate as speakers in the identification, characterization, and reuse of mining environmental liabilities and

primary and secondary mineral resources. Dates for these virtual workshops and programme is being outlined. As a preliminary schedule, we expect to be running such events starting around M24, slightly before or even after, so details have not been defined yet.

Both expert groups have enough material already developed to create the content of the workshops to be taught. On the other hand, the internal communication actions of ASGMI's wide network allow for visibility of these events. In addition, other international organizations (EuroGeoSurveys, European Federation of Geologists, EIT Raw Materials, professional geological associations of different countries, etc.) with which ASGMI already has connections can be contacted to contribute both to the agenda of speakers and the dissemination of the event so that it has the desired number of registrations. ASGMI's geological surveys also have contact with the main universities in their respective countries, so the appropriate audience can be reached through them.

4.3.3 Other training opportunities

4.3.3.1 Portuguese Society of Materials (SPM)

The technical division “Materials for Energy” of the Portuguese Society of Materials will organize in September 2023 (6th-8th) the second edition of the summer school called “Materials for Energy Transition”⁵. This event will be held at the premises of the Portuguese Engineers Order in Porto, Portugal. At the moment, the program is still being outlined but the inclusion in the technical program of a presentation of the START project is foreseen, as well as the provision of promotional information about the project (roller banner and leaflets). This event is aimed at students or young scientists, with the first edition taking place in September 2022, and with around 30 participants.

Figure 9: Banner of the 2nd edition of the Summer School on “Materials for Energy Transition”.

4.3.3.2 Training in synergy with clustered projects and initiatives

In the framework of the clustering activities (Task 6.4) START will see if joint training activities can be organised together with other projects or initiatives that share some of the main interests of the

⁵ <https://spmateriais.pt/site/materials-for-energy-transition/>

project, like mine waste exploitation, raw materials issues, energy harvesting, green energy, etc. No plan is present yet, but this would be a way to make the collaborations concrete and measurable.

4.3.3.3 The START webinars

Although not purely training events, also the webinars will disseminate useful information and educate to the topics of thermoelectricity, mine waste recovery, waste heat recovery, etc. Three of them have been organised: on 28/02/2023, 26/04/2023 and 31/05/2023. Details on these events can be retrieved in Deliverable D6.4.

4.3.4 Final Workshop

The final Training Workshop, according to what indicated in the initial proposal, will be both for scientists and industry members, and focused on sustainability of the developed know-how. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants, probably in a hybrid format. The actual contents, the duration and all details will clearly be decided much later, beginning the organisation at the end of the third year of the project.